

HOMOEOPATHIC MANAGEMENT IN MIGRAINE: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIALS

K. Grace Pravallika, *Post Graduate Scholar, Department of Homoeopathic Repertory, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Homoeopathic Medical College, Pune.*

Jyoti D Patil, *Associate Professor, Department of Homoeopathic Repertory, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Homoeopathic Medical College Pune.*

ABSTRACT

Migraine is a common neurological problem in day-to-day life. It affects 15% of women and 6% of men and first among young women of the global population. Careful examination and assessing the patient are the key to treating migraine headache patients. Nowadays people are more opting to improve their quality of life with holistic approaches and alternative therapies rather than pharmacological treatment but there is no clear evidence or studies that migraine can be completely cured in Homoeopathy. This review on homoeopathic management is based on considering RCT and this systematic review's objective was to assess the clinical studies that looked at the effectiveness of Homoeopathy in included randomised placebo-controlled studies. In some studies, homoeopathic treatments work well and the remaining studies suggest that Homoeopathy is not beyond placebo or equal. In some studies, there is no significant proof that Homoeopathy is more effective than a placebo in the treatment of headaches and migraine.

KEYWORDS: Migraine, Homoeopathy, randomised controlled trials, systematic review, meta-analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Migraine is the second most common cause of the headache and the most common headache-related, and indeed a neurologic, cause of disability in the world this type of neurological headache is characterised by recurrent attacks from moderate to severe symptoms of a migraine, throbbing pain or pulsating sensation in one area of the head and is normally accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and intense sensitivity to light, sound, smell, feeling sick, vomiting, painful headache, and disturbed vision. The cause of migraine is unknown but there is increasing evidence that the aura is due to the dysfunction of ion channels causing a spreading front of cortical depolarisation (excitation) followed by hyperpolarisation (depression of activity). This process spreads over the cortex at a rate of about 3 mm/minute, corresponding to the aura's symptomatic spread. The headache phase is associated with vasodilatation of extracranial vessels and may be relayed by hypothalamic activity. Activation of the trigeminovascular system is probably important. Various factors trigger migraine and triggering factors may vary from patient to patient. Migraine without aura is more common than with aura and most of the time it is misdiagnosed with sinusitis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This systematic approach is crucial in ensuring the study's reliability and validity. The study focused on human populations, specifically individuals involved in Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs). This choice was made to ensure that the research findings were directly applicable to the target demographic of human patients.

The intervention of interest in this study was Homoeopathy. Therefore, the inclusion criteria required that the selected articles pertained to Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs) involving homoeopathic treatments. To establish the effectiveness of homoeopathic treatments, the Researcher ensured that the selected articles had a clear comparison with a placebo group. This was crucial to assess the relative impact of homoeopathic treatments in comparison to a control group receiving a placebo. To maintain the rigor of the study, the Researcher selected articles that had a specific sample size in two groups. This criterion was essential for statistical analysis and to draw meaningful conclusions about the

efficacy of Homoeopathy. To access a comprehensive pool of relevant articles, the Researcher searched electronic databases that included The Cochrane Library, HomBRex, Google Scholar, CORE-HOM, and PubMed. This choice of databases ensured that a wide range of sources was considered, enhancing the study's comprehensiveness and the ability to draw reliable conclusions.

Exclusion Criteria:

To maintain the focus and relevance of the study, the Researcher also applied exclusion criteria. Articles that did not pertain to Homoeopathy were excluded from consideration. Additionally, animal studies were not included in the selection process as the primary focus was on human trials. By meticulously applying these criteria, the Researcher ensured that the selected articles for the study were highly relevant, met stringent quality standards, and provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of homoeopathic treatments in RCTs involving human subjects. This methodological approach enhances the reliability and credibility of the research findings.

Fig.1. Prisma flow chart

RESULTS

Data extraction from available RCTs and A total of five RCTs on headaches and migraine and five studies were discovered that they met mentioned inclusion/exclusion criteria. Table 1 compiles the important information from each study that was included.

Table 1. Overview of randomised controlled studies

S.no Reference	Setting	Study design	Sample size	Interventions	Drop out	Follow up	Outcome	Result
Brigo 1991	Italy	Randomised	60	Group A- If similimum was among 8 predefined remedies in 30c potency doses in interval of 2weeks. Group B- Placebo	None	4 Months	Significant result shown in favour of Homoeopathy	Improvement is significant in Homoeopathy than placebo
Walach 1997	Germany	Randomised	98	Group A- Individualised similimum and dosage Group B- placebo	6	5 Months	Mild decrease in headache and frequency	Improvement in both groups no significant difference
Whitmarsh 1997	UK	Randomised	63	Group A- If similimum was among 11 predefined remedies in 30c potency doses in interval of 2weeks. Group B- Placebo	3	4 Months	Frequency was decreased	No significant difference shown in two groups
Straumsheim 1997	Norway	Randomised	64	Group A- Individualised similimum and dosage from available 60 remedies Group B- Placebo	68 completed study	4 Months	Decreased in frequency and intensity	Similar outcome has shown in both groups
Niranjan Mohanty 2020	Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India	Randomised	60	Group A- Individualised similimum and dosage Group B- Placebo	0	6 months	Decreased in frequency and intensity	Improvement is significant in only Homoeopathy

DISCUSSION

A thorough search for homoeopathic trials was first done. Then, it was only concentrated on prevention trials. This systematic review only included randomised, placebo-controlled, double-blind clinical studies. Trials comparing one homoeopathic potency to another or Homoeopathy to other forms of therapy were not included.

Sample size 60 migraine sufferers were randomly assigned to groups A and B by Brigo and Serpelloni. The authors did not specify their precise migraine diagnostic standards. At 2-week intervals, each patient got one oral therapy dosage. Six homoeopathic treatments were available in group A, each of which was individually prescribed in 30C potency. Placebos were supplied to group B. At weeks 8 and 16, patient diaries were used to assess the effectiveness of the treatment. All outcome factors show a considerable favourability for Homoeopathy.

98 patients were randomly assigned to Group A or Group B by Walach and colleagues. 66% percent of these individuals had migraines, and 51% had headaches of the tension variety. Group A got customised homoeopathic treatments (individualised similimum) following a 6-week run-in phase, whereas group B received placebos. Twelve weeks were spent on treatment. The intended result was a decrease in headache frequency, severity, and duration but there was no significant difference between the two groups.

63 patients according to International Headache Society (IHS) criteria, Whitmarsh and colleagues¹¹ randomly assigned 63 migraine sufferers to either group A or B. Both teams were given a placebo for a trial duration of one month all potencies of 30C. For three months, patients were directed to take two pills twice a week. Group B was given an identical placebo. It revealed a significant difference between the two groups.

73 patients were randomly divided into groups A and B by Straumsheim et al. In all, 68 patients completed the research. After a one-month "run-in" period, group A got customised treatments (from a list of 60 treatments in three potencies), whereas group B received identical placebos for four months. Clinical results were assessed using patient diaries and neurologist evaluation. They continuously kept a record of all referrals, homoeopathic prescriptions, and conventional therapeutic usage. The first three months showed a marked improvement in the severity of diagnoses (as determined by physicians) and medical complaints (as determined by patients or their parents), and this typically persisted throughout the whole monitoring period.

60 patients are followed screening, and divided into two groups, a test group of 30 and a control group of 30 by Niranjana Mohant et al. The control group received the same placebo as the test group, which received homoeopathic medications. Headache Impact Test (HIT) 6 was used to evaluate intensity. Scores on the HIT were kept both during and after therapy. The trial lasted for six months. The incidence was greater in the second and fourth decades of life and decreased in the elderly. Females were more likely to be afflicted than males. The difference between the groups was observed using a paired t-test, which revealed statistical significance ($p < 0.0001$). Natrum muriaticum was the homoeopathic drug that was most frequently recommended.

In a Meta-analysis Homoeopathy's mode of action might be referred to as systemic. However, the database comprises too few studies and trials with conflicting results, which prevents any comprehensive synthesis. Prospective studies were done one among them concluded. The results demonstrate the interest of homoeopathic medicines for the preventing and treatment of migraine attacks in children. A significant decrease in the frequency, severity, and duration of migraine attacks was observed, consequently, reduced absenteeism from school. Another observational research concludes that individuals with migraine show significant and sustained improvements after receiving Homoeopathy medication.

CONCLUSION

The evidence from previous RCTs was not in favor of a specific effect from homoeopathic remedies. These studies, however, included only a very select group of patients and they have a low external

validity. Future research trials and studies should help resolve this. Since homoeopathic remedies did not outperform a placebo in RCTs for migraine headache relief, it's difficult to conclude. In some studies, there is no significant proof that Homoeopathy is more effective than a placebo in the treatment of headaches and migraine due to the amount of research material and studies being very less amount. If the trials are rigorous and large in sample size, more independent confirmation replications are necessary to come. Although the study's findings are undoubtedly positive, its sample size is quite small. The number of well-established polychrest homoeopathic medications and certain uncommon treatments that may be useful in the treatment of migraines is relatively small. Additionally, there are several facets of Homoeopathy to investigate, all of which require a bigger sample size to be confirmed.

REFERENCES

- Brigo B, Serpelloni G. Homoeopathic treatment of migraines: a randomized, double-blind study of sixty cases (homoeopathic remedy versus placebo). *Berl J Res Hom* 1991;1:98-106
- Charles A. The migraine aura. *Continuum: Lifelong Learning in Neurology*. 2018 Aug 1;24(4):1009-22.
- Danno K, Colas A, Masson JL, Bordet MF. Homoeopathic treatment of migraine in children: results of a prospective, multicentre, observational study. *The Journal of Alternative and complementary medicine*. 2013 Feb 1;19(2):119-23.
- Ernst E, Pittler MH. The efficacy of homoeopathic Arnica: a systematic review of placebo-controlled clinical trials. *Arch Surgery* 1998;133:1187-1190
- Grabia S, Ernst E. Homoeopathic aggravations: a systematic review of randomized, placebo-controlled clinical trials. *Homoeopathy* 2003;92:92-8.
- Khadim A, Nuruzzaman M. Efficacy of Homoeopathic Medicine in the Treatment of Migraine: A Literature Review. *Intl J Creative Res Thoughts*. 2020 May;8(5):248-54.
- Khalsa D. An efficacious homoeopathic treatment for acute migraine headache. *Biomed Therapy* 1998;15:223-224
- Linde K, Clausius N, Ramirez G, Melchart D, Eitel F, Hedges LV, Jonas W. Are the clinical effects of Homoeopathy placebo effects? A meta-analysis of placebo-controlled trials. *Lancet* 1997;350:834-843.
- Mohanty N, Sahoo AR, Choudhury S, Jena SK. Homoeopathy in the treatment of migraine: A randomized placebo-controlled clinical trial.
- Peroutka SJ. What turns on a migraine? A systematic review of migraine precipitating factors. *Current pain and headache reports*. 2014 Oct;18(10):454.
- Silberstein SD. Migraine symptoms: Results of a survey of self-reported migraineurs. *Headache: The Journal of Head and Face Pain*. 1995 Jul;35(7):387-96.2.
- Stephen D, Silberstein MD. Migraine symptoms; Results of a survey of self-reported Migraineurs, Headache. *The Journal of Head and Pain*. 1995;35(7):387-96.
- Straumsheim P, Borchgrevink C, Mowinckel P, Kierulf P, et al. Homoeopathic treatment of migraine: a double-blind, placebo-controlled trial of 68 patients. *Br Hom J* 2000;89:4-7.
- Thabane L, Thomas T, Ye C, Paul J. Posing the research question: not so simple. *Canadian Journal of Anesthesia/Journal canadien d'anesthésie*. 2009 Jan 1;56(1):71-9.
- Subhranil S, Munmun K. Homoeopathic treatment of headaches & migraine: a meta-analysis of the randomized controlled trials. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*. 2013;6(3):194-9.
- Walach H, Haeusler W, Lowes T, Mussbach D, et al. Classical homoeopathic treatment of chronic headache. *Cephalgia* 1997;17:119-26.
- Walach H, Haag G. Homoeopathy in headaches. A review. *Schmerz* 1996 Jun;10(3):156-62.
- Whitmarsh TE, Coltston-Shields DM, Steiner TJ. Double-blind randomized placebo-controlled study of homoeopathic prophylaxis of migraine. *Cephalgia* 1997;17:600-4.

Witt CM, Luedtke R, Willich SN. Homoeopathic treatment of chronic headache (ICD-9: 784.0)—a prospective observational study with 2-year follow-up. *Complementary Medicine Research*. 2009;16(4):227-35.

Yang M, Rendas-Baum R, Varon SF, Kosinski M. Validation of the Headache Impact Test (HIT-6TM) across episodic and chronic migraine. *Cephalalgia* [Internet]. 2011 Feb [cited 2014 Jun 6]; 31 (3): 357–67.